

CHEMISTRY SCIENCES

COMPOSITIONS BASED ON EPOXY RESINS ARE FILLED WITH DIFFERENT FILLERS (Overview)

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Abstract

The review considers scientific works devoted to composite materials based on a filled epoxy oligomer. Filling the epoxy oligomer with various fillers improves the performance properties of compositions based on them. A number of formulations of composites based on epoxy resin have been analyzed and the effect of some fillers and modifiers on their properties has been shown. The properties of composites based on epoxy oligomer (EDO) and wood ash (DR) have been studied. As a result of research, it was proved that the addition of WA increases the impact strength of the composition by 2 times, increases the density up to 40%, the hardness of the composite gradually increases with increasing WA content. A uniform distribution of WA particles in the matrix has been obtained.

Keywords: filler, epoxy oligomer, composite materials, basalt, compounds, shells, of cow bone, three ash.

Epoxy polymers have such a complex of properties (adhesion, mechanical, electrical, etc.), which in many cases makes them irreplaceable as a basis for adhesives, paint coatings, compounds and reinforced plastics. Thanks to this, epoxy resins have occupied an important place in the range of industrial polymer materials.

The production of epoxy resins began with research conducted in the US and Europe on the eve of the Second World War. The first resins, the products of the reaction epichlorohydrin with bisphenol A, were obtained on an industrial scale in 1947. Over 10 years their production level was over 13.6 thousand tons, in the next six years their production level increased threefold. In the late 50's, new epoxy resins were obtained, other than diglycidyl ether; In late 1960, the industry mastered the production of at least 25 types of resins. At this stage, the term "epoxy resin" becomes general and is currently applied to a large family of materials.

Epoxy resins belong to the class of thermosetting plastics and are similar to such materials as phenols and polyesters. A number of valuable properties of epoxy resins led to their widespread use in industry. Epoxy resins are universal due to their small shrinkage, ease of curing, good chemical resistance and extremely high strength of the glue joint.

But epoxy is not without flaws. Exactly in some cases the high viscosity, low thermal and flammability of epoxide oligomers.

One of the effective ways to control the properties of this oligomer is their modification. In this regard, the actual task is to search for modifiers. The discovery of specific features of modification additives and purposeful use of their optimal technological, physical and mechanical, adhesion, optical properties allows controlling the processes of collecting materials on their basis.

Recently, most attention has been paid to adding strong compounds to the polymer mesh. In this case, phosphorus, nitrogen-containing compounds convert EO into high-grade and heat-resistant materials, durability, adhesion properties.

The development of various sectors of the economy requires the creation of highly effective composite materials, which involves the search for new promising fillers. At the same time, modern economic conditions require the production of composites, not only with a high set of characteristics, but also affordable, with a fairly low cost. Therefore, the great potential for improving the characteristics of composite materials lies in the use of inexpensive and effective fillers, including, of course, basalt and its derivatives. Unique properties of basalt make it one of the most popular materials. Basalt is non-flammable and able to withstand temperatures up to 900°C, is durable and resistant to mechanical influences, has high sound and heat insulating properties, biological resistance, and chemical neutrality - resistant to corrosive acid and alkaline media, does not accumulate radiation. Basalt is environmentally friendly and harmless for humans and animals [1].

In this paper, we investigated the possibility of using basalt as a filler of an epoxy compound consisting of epoxy resin grade ED-20, hardener polyethylene polyamine (PEPA) and a multifunctional action modifier - trichloroethyl phosphate (TCEP). The preparation of basalt consisted in its grinding and fractionation. The investigated filler has a significant particle size distribution, which is confirmed by optical microscopy data. The possibility of creating highly filled compositions is proved. The introduction of 50 wt / h of basalt into the composition provides high values of the properties. It should be noted that in epoxy compositions, crushed

basalt behaves as an active filler that enhances properties. And this is manifested as an increase in mechanical properties - Brinell hardness, resistance to static and dynamic bending (impact) more than doubles, and physico-chemical - heat resistance also increases from 114 to 206°C. When studying the thermal stability of samples with thermogravimetric analysis, it was noted: an increase in coke residues, a decrease in pyrolysis rates, a significant decrease (more than twofold), mass losses up to 600°C / g. The revealed influence of dispersed basalt on the pyrolysis of epoxy resin is also manifested in the behavior of the material during combustion in air. Samples containing 30 and 50 parts by weight basalt do not support combustion in air and the weight loss is 1.4 and 0.7%, respectively. Thus, the efficiency and expediency of using ground epoxy resin for ground basalt is proved, without processing it into fibers. An increase in the physicochemical and mechanical properties of compositions filled with basalts has been established, which allows expanding the scope of basalt application to create a wide range of use of PCM [2].

The use of magnesium oxide (MgO) as a filler in an epoxy molding compound (EMC) was considered to identify the maximum thermal conductivity that could be achieved without compromising rheological or processing control and processing flexibility. MgO is an attractive candidate filler for EMCs used in automotive and other applications because MgO is inexpensive, electrically insulative, has relatively high thermal conductivity, is nontoxic, and is a relatively soft filler material meaning it will be less abrasive to surfaces it contacts during its processing and shape molding. EPOXY molding compounds (EMCs) are used in a multitude of electronic and electric motor component applications, and for those specifically used

or considered for automotive application, low cost has equivalent importance as service performance. Optical microscopy images of the two used MgO powders. The powder on the left is designated as 10C and that on the right is 50C [1], [2].

A bulk thermal conductivity up to 3 W/mK can be achieved with concomitant low cost if MgO is used as a filler in an EMC. This is a 10× increase in thermal conductivity compared with unfilled epoxy and about twice that of traditional SiO₂ filled EMCs. The MgO-filled EMCs also had a higher thermal diffusivity than SiO₂-filled EMCs, meaning thermal transfer occurs more quickly in the MgO-filled EMCs. MgO-filled EMCs possess electrically insulative, thermal expansion, and water absorption characteristics that are equivalent to those of traditional silica-filled EMCs. The results signify that MgO EMCs would be more effective than SiO₂-EMCs at lowering the maximum temperature of encapsulated components. Obtaining a thermal conductivity of >3 W/mK using MgO would require a filler content greater than 56 vol%; however, a higher volume fraction would compromise and limit rheological control during the transfer molding process. Given this, the authors assert that 3 W/mK is the highest thermal conductivity achievable for a low-cost, electrically insulative, nontoxic EMC with versatile flow characteristics and with thermal expansion and water absorption responses equivalent to silica-filled EMCs. Epoxy-based composites Al particles and milled fibres SEM image of the fracture surface of an aluminium filled epoxy; (b) fracture surface of the unfilled epoxy; (c) fracture surface of the aluminium filled epoxy resin (fig.3) (more brittle and stiffer) [5].

Polished cross sections of the six different test sets at 200 × magnification.

Fig.1.

Fig. 2. Epoxy-based composites Al particles and milled fibres SEM image of the fracture surface of an aluminium filled epoxy; (b) fracture surface of the unfilled epoxy; (c) fracture surface of the aluminium filled epoxy resin

The thermal conductivity of epoxy resin composites filled with combustion-synthesized hexagonal boron nitride (h-BN) particles was investigated. The mixing of the composite constituents was carried out by either a dry method (involving no use of solvent) for low filler loadings or a solvent method (using acetone as solvent) for higher filler loadings. It was found that surface treatment of the h-BN particles using the silane 3-glycidoxypropyltrimethoxysilane (GPTMS) increases the thermal conductivity of the resultant composites in a lesser amount compared to the values reported by other studies. Thermal conductivity of cresol Novolac epoxy (CNE) resin filled with combustion-synthesized h-BN particles was investigated. Surface treatment of the h-BN particles with 3-glycidoxypropyltrimethoxysilane (GPTMS) was found to increase the thermal conductivity of the composites by 7.7%–35.4%, which is less than a value reported in another study at a high filler content. This was explained by the fact that the combustion synthesized h-BN contains less –OH or active sites on the surface, thus adsorbing less amount of GPTMS. However, the thermal conductivity of composites filled with the combustion synthesized h-BN were found to be comparable to that with commercially available h-BN reported in other studies. The thermal conductivity of the composites was found to be higher when larger h-BN particles were used. The thermal conductivity was also found to increase with increasing filler content to a maximum and then begin to decrease with further increases in this content. In addition to the effect of higher porosity at higher filler contents, more horizontally oriented h-BN particles formed at higher filler loadings (perhaps due to pressing during formation of the composites) were suggested to be a factor causing this decrease of the thermal conductivity. The measured thermal conductivities were compared to theoretical predictions based on the Nielsen and Lewis theory. The theoretical predictions were found to be lower than the experimental values at low filler contents (<60 vol %) and became increasing higher than the experimental values at high filler contents (>60 vol %) [6].

The influence of the silver-carbonate microdispers particles on the properties of epoxide resin has been

investigated. The effects of Ag_2CO_3 microdispers particles on the thermophysical properties of the epoxide composition have been revealed as a result of experiments.

Thermal linear expansion coefficient of materials that can be used in different temperature ranges was established. Temperature ranges, at which the structural transformations occur, namely, the deformation of epoxy binder macrochains and segments and chemical bonds destruction, were also identified by complex analysis. Conclusion, Permissible temperature ranges, at which the use of epoxy composites filled with silver carbonate is possible, were set on the basis of thermal properties testing using modern research methods. Economically expedient to input minimum Ag_2CO_3 amount in epoxy binder ($q = 0,025$ wt %) for the formation of a composite material or a protective coating with enhanced thermophysical properties, since the Martens heat resistance value for the selected range of filler content does not significantly change – $\Delta T = 358\text{--}360$ K. The behavior of developed composites under the thermal field influence was investigated. Experimentally established that composites containing Ag_2CO_3 particles of $q = 0,500$ wt % are advisable to use at the maximum temperatures range of $\Delta T = 303\text{--}473$ K. Such materials are characterized by the lowest value of thermal linear expansion coefficient, which is $\alpha = 6,84 \times 10^{-5}$ K $^{-1}$. Electrical performance of epoxy resin filled with micro particles and nanoparticles, composite products are also suffering from issues such as low tracking resistance and early failures. The use of nano or micro fillers is considered to be one of the methods that can further improve the properties of the composite product. This study is aimed to study the electrical properties of nano and micro filled epoxy resin. SiO_2 and Al_2O_3 nano and micro fillers are used in this research for comparison purposes. The host matrix, which is epoxy resin, is filled with nano particles, micro particles or both nano and micro particles. Micro particles and nano particles are dispersed into epoxy resin using planetary centrifugal mixing technique and degassed in vacuum. In total, seven types of materials are prepared in this study. These materials are neat epoxy, nanocomposite filled with 1 wt% nano SiO_2 fillers, micro-composite filled with 20 wt% micro SiO_2

fillers, micro-nano composite filled with 1 wt% nano SiO₂ and 20 wt% micro SiO₂ fillers, nanocomposite filled with 1 wt% nano Al₂O₃ fillers, micro-composite filled with 20 wt% micro Al₂O₃ fillers, micro-nano composite filled with 1 wt% nano Al₂O₃ and 20 wt% micro Al₂O₃ fillers. In this study, AC electrical breakdown strength test are performed using a sphere-to-sphere setup. The thickness of all the samples is 1 mm ± 0.1 mm in accordance to the IEC standard. Surface partial discharge measurement is also performed to evaluate the surface property. All of the filled specimens show an improvement in the dielectric strength. The breakdown strength of nano-micro-composite increased from 32.45 kV to 34.45kV (Al₂O₃ specimens) and 34.6kV (SiO₂ specimens). Al₂O₃ specimens showed a better resistance against surface discharge. The experimental results can be concluded as follows. A higher breakdown strength is recorded from nanocomposite samples compare to neat epoxy. Micro-composite showed an improvement in breakdown strength due to the improvement in dispersion using centrifugal mixing method and high vacuum degassing procedure. Better dispersion created larger interface area between the particles and epoxy resin matrix and eventually leads to an increase in breakdown strength. Adding nano particles into micro-composite can further increase the breakdown strength of the material. Similar results are observed in the breakdown strength test of Al₂O₃ and SiO₂ particles. A significant improvement in surface PD resistance is observed on the nanocomposites. Al₂O₃ nano fillers successfully reduced both of the dissipation current and PD counts by more than 99% at 5kV. The SiO₂ samples also reduced the dissipation current and PD counts by 66.4% and 92.9% respectively.

Different nano- and micro-fillers are added to modify the mechanical properties, wear resistance, thermal properties and the curing process of polymers. A very important application for epoxy resins is to be used as coating for anti-cavitation painting. Pyrogenic silica is already used in adhesives and paints, being its application related to rheology. The objective of this work is to study the effect of pyrogenic silica on epoxy resins, usually not present in their formulation. SiO₂/epoxy nanocomposites with two different loads of nano-silica, 3 and 5 wt% were manufactured. In particular, the study focuses on the influence that the addition of nano-silica has on the mechanical, wear and cavitation erosion properties as well as on the thermal properties and the curing reaction. To accomplish these goals, nanocomposite samples in bulk and as coating were prepared. Mechanical properties (hardness, bending and tensile strength), wear resistance (in bulk and coating) and cavitation erosion were evaluated. The epoxy curing process and the influence of nano-SiO₂ additions on the glass transition temperature (tg) were studied by Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC). In general, a plasticising effect was observed with nano-silica addition. Moreover, the resistance to erosion by cavitation, in terms of cumulative erosion and erosion rate, was higher for the nanocomposites than for clear resin. The wear is influenced by the addition of nanoparticles. Nanocomposites H₅SiO₂ must not be used for

applications with requirements of a high wear resistance. A lower content of silica (3%) should be used, especially for “in-bulk” applications, as seen for the lubricating effect observed at 1000 m sliding distance. All cavitation erosion parameters are reduced adding nano-SiO₂, although a difference between additions of 3% and 5% cannot be appreciated. The tests have shown a decrement in cumulative mass loss and an increment in incubation time. The cavitation resistance improvement is due to the increment in root shape fractures and plastic deformation in some areas. Mechanical properties are also affected by nano-SiO₂ addition. The composite tends to have less strength and hardness, but be more ductile. Also, its Young's modulus decreases when a larger percentage is added. Lower tg values indicate that the nanocomposites plasticise more with respect to clear resin. The observed plasticisation is consistent with the loss of strength and hardness together with augmented ductility. Nano-particles also affect the curing process, promoting the initial curing mechanism (autocatalytic reaction), but in high amount they hinder crosslinking and the total curing is inhibited.

The reinforcement by high strength fibers provides the polymer substantially enhanced mechanical properties and makes them more suitable for a large number of diverse applications. This research evaluates the effects of particulate Cow bone and Groundnut shell additions on the mechanical properties and microstructure of cow bone and groundnut shell reinforced epoxy composite in order to assess the possibility of using it as a material for engineering applications. Cow bone and groundnut shell particles reinforced with epoxy (CBRPC and GSRPC) was prepared by varying the cow bone and groundnut shell particles from 0-25 wt% with 5 wt% intervals. The results revealed that mechanical properties did not increase uniformly with additions in filler but exhibited maximum properties at specific percentages of filler additions. From the Microscopic evaluation, it was discovered that homogeneity decreases with increase in % filler, this could be due to poor interfacial bonding. Natural-fiber composites with thermoplastic and thermoset matrices have been used for various applications such as car manufacturing and suppliers for door panels, package trays, dashboards and interior parts. Natural fibers cultivation depends mainly on solar energy. For the natural fiber production, processing and extractions, relatively small amount of fossil fuel energy is required. While in comparison, the production of synthetic fiber depends mainly on fossil fuels and needs nearly ten times more energy as compared to natural fiber. As a result, the pollutant gas emissions to the environment from synthetic fiber production are significantly higher than that from the natural fiber production. Agunsoye studied the effects of particulate cow bone additions on the mechanical properties and tribological behavior of cow bone reinforced polyethylene composite in order to assess the possibility of using it as a new material for engineering applications. The results revealed that tensile strength and the hardness values of the composite increased with increase in wt.% cow bone

particles while the impact strength and rigidity decreased. The study also revealed that the additions of the particulate cow bone have the most significant main effect on the wear behavior of the composite while the interactions between load and time has no significant. Hence, cow bone particles could be used to improve the strength and wear properties of recycled low density polyethylene (RLDPE). Isiaka investigated the influence of cow bone particle size distribution on the mechanical properties of polyester matrix composites in order to consider the suitability of the materials as biomaterials. It was discovered that fine cow bone particles lead to improved strength while coarse particles lead to improved toughness. The results also

showed that these materials are structurally compatible and are being developed from animal fiber based particle. It is expected to also aid the compatibility with the surface conditions as biomaterials. From the literatures, it is clear that natural fibres can be used to reinforce polymeric materials and get composite material with improve mechanical properties. In this research, the relationship between the microstructure and mechanical properties of groundnut shell, cow bone and a hybrid of groundnut shell and cow bone reinforced with epoxy is investigated in order to evaluate their uses as an engineering material and a biomaterial respectively.

Fig.3. Cow bone as filler

In experimental studies, the mechanical properties of the epoxy oligomer were significantly changed in the rectilinear direction. It can be seen that the hybrid sample of 5% reinforcement showed the highest resistance before shattering relative to other samples the flexural test was performed on. This implies that the hybrid reinforcement of 5% can be used in place of the pure epoxy for applications where flexibility is a major consideration. That the groundnut shell sample of 20% reinforcement showed the highest stiffness before shattering relative to other samples the tensile test was performed on. Therefore, the groundnut shell reinforcement of 20% can be used in place of pure epoxy where stiffness is a major concern. that the hybrid sample of 5% reinforcement showed to have the highest surface hardness compared to all other samples being tested. This implies that the hybrid reinforcement of 5% can be used in place of the pure epoxy for applications where surface hardness is a major consideration. That the hybrid sample of 15% reinforcement showed to absorb the highest amount of energy before shattering relative to other samples the impact test was performed on. Therefore, the hybrid reinforcement of 15% can be used in place of pure epoxy where impact strength is a major concern. That as the filler concentration increased, the shapes of the reinforcement became larger, changed from spherically shaped to irregularly shaped and they became more closely packed.

This paper presents the study of the tensile, compressive, flexural, impact energy and water absorption characteristics of the luffa fiber and Ground nut reinforced epoxy polymer hybrid composites. Luffa fiber and Ground nut reinforced epoxy resin matrix

composites have been developed by hand lay-up technique with luffa fiber treated conditions and Ground nut with different volume fraction of fibers as in 1:1 ratio (10%, 20%, 30%, 40% and 50%). Effects of volume fraction on the Tensile, Compressive, Flexural, Impact strength were studied. SEM analysis on the composite materials was performed. Tensile strength varies from 10.35 MPa to 19.31 MPa, compressive strength varies from 26.66 MPa to 52.22 MPa, flexural strength varies from 35.75 MPa to 58.95 MPa and impact energy varies from 0.6 Joules to 1.3 Joules, as a function of fiber volume fraction. The optimum mechanical properties were obtained at 40% of fiber volume fraction of treated fiber composites. Fractures surface of the composite shows the pull out and debonding of fiber is occurred. The variation of compressive, impact, tensile and flexural properties of the luffa fiber and groundnut reinforced epoxy polymer hybrid composites for 10%, 20%, 30%, 40%, and 50% fibers content were studied as a function of alkali treatment. It is reported that composites having 40% treated fiber content exhibited higher values for the fore mentioned properties than luffa groundnut fiber polymer composites with 30% and 50% fibre contents. The mechanical property values of luffa – groundnut reinforced composite were slightly higher than that of luffa fibre reinforced composite. After the alkali treatment, it was found that, treated composites possessed higher values of aforementioned mechanical properties because the alkali treatment improves the adhesive characteristics of the surface of the luffa fibers and groundnut by removal of hemicelluloses, waxes, impurities and lignin from the fibers. In the present work, it was found that optimum values and significant

improvements were at 40% treated fiber reinforced composites. The morphology of fractured surface observed by SEM suggests that the networking of structure restricts the pull out of fiber, which is responsible for higher mechanical properties for 40 % fiber content. The decrease in strength at 50% fiber content is due to insufficient wetting of fiber with the matrix.

The present work aims at investigating the effect of locally produced clay (Algeria), along with the effect of their size and rate on physical and mechanical properties of the composite material. This study is divided into two parts: The first one is devoted to the study of the composite material based on epoxy resin with kaolin, using different size fractions at rates ranging from 2% to 20%. The second part examines epoxy resin-based composite with calcined kaolin (meta kaolin) with regard to the influence of the structure, the particle size and the charge rate on the properties of the material. It is shown that the clay fillers give the epoxy resin different properties compared to the epoxy resin alone and, additionally, reduce the cost of materials. It was also observed that the fillers enhance the mechanical properties by increasing the rigidity of the material. There is a maximum value of 2.4 GPa to 18% kaolin, or more than 325% increase in the modulus of elasticity with respect to unfilled resin for the finer particle size. It was also found that the modulus of elasticity increases with increasing the loading rate. Indeed, the rigidity increases with increasing the filler rate. Moreover, for both fillers, lower fraction yields better results. Moreover, for both types of added fillers, lower fraction yields better results.

Epoxy resins are characterized by significant thermosetting resins that are used for matrix surfaces for aerospace or hydro - cosmic production, for the

perfect mechanic readability, good heat, electrical and chemical stability, insulating materials for electrotechnical and electronical production, materials for reconstruction and other materials. At the same time, there is a low productivity of the products, which is distributed to the thresholds and is not expensive. Calcium carbonate, used in this study, was found in Rama 's crucible shells. CaCO_3 uses the biological epoxide system of biological resources. Potential biosecond implants can be used in the epoxy resin and CaCO_3 , based on the use of calcium carbonate calcium and calcium phosphate, as well as calcium calcium. The choice of p-amino benzoic acid (p-ABA) in the solidification agent is based on the fact that the ten is a non-toxic product used in a medical and human body. The literary texts indicate that what is being studied is directed to the acquisition of p-ABA in the epithelial agent of the coupling agent [22].

Preparation of bio-based CaCO_3 Natural CaCO_3 as an inorganic filler was obtained from the conch shell of Rapana thomasiana (harvested from Romanian beach of Black Sea) using the following procedure: Hundred gram R, thomasiana conch shell was ground in a laboratory type ball-mill, washed with deionized water and dried at 105 C. After drying, the conch shell sample was heated at 600 C for 4 h to remove the organic part. 55 g CaCO_3 were obtained and were again ground into fine powder. The majority of CaCO_3 particle's size has values around 57 μm .

In the work, the fillers for the compositions were obtained from the preparation of a number of stages that were processed in the laboratory. The fillers were obtained from the shell collected from the coast of the Caspian Sea, the beach area in the territory of the Republic of Azerbaijan (from the coast of Nardaran).

Fig. 4. Preparation of filler and composite

In the study, it was found that composites based on the epoxide of the CaCO_3 -containing agglomeration of the particles were observed upon the addition of an excess of filler. This reduced the adhesive properties between the filler and the matrix and in turn led to a reduction in the hardness of the compositions.

The properties of the composite are improved by adding the shell by 35% to the epoxy matrix. As the amount of filler increases, elasticity and hardness decrease. The study describes the ultimate strength, softening point and water absorption of polymeric composites based on epoxy resin (type ED-20) with

unmodified and / or modified mineral diatomite of tetraethoxysilane (TEOS). Comparison of the experimental results obtained for the investigated composites shows that those containing modified filler have higher technical parameters mentioned above than composites with unmodified filler at the appropriate loading. Experimentally is shown that the composites containing binary fillers diatomite and andesite at definite ratio of them possess the optimal characteristics – so called synergistic effect. Experimental results are explained in terms of structural peculiarities of polymer composites.

Comparison of the density, ultimate strength, softening temperature and water absorption for polymer composites based on epoxy resin and unmodified and modified by tetraethoxysilane mineral fillers diatomite and andesite leads to conclusion that modify agent stipulates the formation of heterogeneous structures with higher compatibility of ingredients and consequently to enhancing of noted above technical characteristics [23-25].

Due to the huge demand in production of environmentally friendly materials application of natural cellulose is very popular in modern industry. Tree ash has been examined as a filler in the epoxy based composite materials in order to optimise material's characteristics. After physico-chemical tests it has been estimated that addition of the tree ash on epoxy oligomer increases physical parameters as elasticity, rate of consolidation, impact resistance, compression strength. Physical analysis has shown 100% increase in impact resistance, 40% increase in extensibility parameters of epoxy based composite materials. Material's hardness gradually changes with increasing amount of added tree ash.

After reaction of tree ash and polymer composition matrix the metal oxide properties in ash content influence parameters of polymer composite material and results in complex changes in property structures. Content of ash CaO, SiO₂ and K₂O gives high fireproof to PKM. Silicagel which has 2,648 q·cm⁻³

density (SiO₂) and 1600-1725°C melting point, Calciumoxide (CaO) 3,5 q·sm⁻³ density and 2572°C melting point, potasium oxide (K₂O) 2,35 q·sm⁻³ density and 350°C melting point. Therefore SiO₂ content increases hardness, chemical and thermal resistance of PKMi. Calcium oxide or othercalled quicklime (CaO) is main content of tree and it also increases mixture's hardness and thermal resistance and increases adhesion force between polymer matrix and other components. Potasium oxide (K₂O) content improves solution and thermal stability of material. Thereby, ash contains specific characteristics of metallic and metal oxide samples [26].

The tree ash prepared from walnut tree at 400⁰ C temperature from thermal pyrolysis procedure in closed container. First coal received from the tree, thereafter coal burned for 5-8 hours at 350 °C temperature to transform into ash.

First of al tree ash prepared, then epoxy oligomer, plasticizer and consolidation agent appropriately mixed.

The mixture of oligomer with other components blended to tree ash. Prepared mixture poured into the mold accurately and constantly in order to make material pores fully loaded. Consolidation proces of the composite takes 24 hour at 60-80°C temperature. After consolidation proces product removed from mold and it's properties investigated.

Table 1.

Properties of composition

Samples	Compression strength, MPa	Impact viscosity, N	Impact resistance, kq/sm	Elasticity, mm
I	57.7	0.99	30	5
II	84.9	0.92	50	1
III	87.2	0.78	50	1
IV	95.2	0.55	40	1
V	104.2	0.54	40	5

Addition of tree ash amount to epoxy based composite material influenced elasticity, impact strength and compression strength. These parameters has relatively changed by addition of fillers to the composite material. This increase is characterised with high interphase energy between epoxy resin and walnut tree ash. Compression strength, impact strength increses, whereas, elasticity of the material decreases by addition of the filler particles [27].

In the last time, natural exponentials are used to obtain new composite materials with high precision and elasticity. Composite material refers to a combination of two or more components. The composites for each component are complemented by individual individualities, which are complemented by other components of the clay property [1-5].

The research has exposed the spectrum of the spectrum used in the coconut orchard in the skill, construction materials, and sailors, fishing boats, furniture and other appliances. In fact, the coconut self-esteem in the quality of the exterior has some of the ecological advantages preceded by ordinary filler. It is also desir-

able to have low energy consumption, low energy consumption, low safety, low density, and specific properties [6, 7].

Activated carbon is also used for the adsorbent treatment of water. The active carbon is represented by a porous carbonic material, which is highly adsorbed and is used in the catalyst and catalyst to improve the adsorbent concentrations of gaseous and fine powder in industrial efficiencies. The active ingredient is widely used in salmon, pharmaceutical, and car and seaweed production [8, 9].

The use of natural volcanoes in the production of plastics rapidly varies, because they magnify the mechanical properties and build up the cost of the composite. The use of natural volcanoes is ecologically pure, with the exception of inorganic fillers.

In the context of this context, there are many potential sources of energy for CO₂ emissions, but not for carbon dioxide in plastics composites. Even though the glasses are widely used in aerospace and transportation regions, there are many shortcomings. What is the use of energy in the process of production, exposure to health, recycling, and removal.

Composite from the natural walnut are ecologically clean in alternatives to glass fibers. The best of the best - a light and low cost natural gas, good sound insulation and soundproofing.

Basic rocks of volatile composites do their own technical materials. By typing in, you can buy the material with unobstructed properties, controlling the selection of the filler, matrices and methods of processing.

In principle, you will be able to get composite materials in an infinite form. Taksim image, based on chaotic oriented and unidirectional volcanoes, can be obtained from a large number of composite materials. In the composites, a large number of combinations are available for the form, size and orientation of the penetrator. The only correct choice of matrixes and enhancer comforters is the acquisition of a guarantee of composite materials with high complexity (4).

It has been noted that composites with volatile composites, derived from disperse repellents, work well in real-world conditions.

Epoxy oligomer is a widely used polymer matrix for composites. However, the strength, low modulus of elasticity of this polymer matrix limits its wider application. To modify the epoxy oligomer with various fillers is very important. Adding a filler to the polymer matrix is one way to quickly and cheaply

change the properties of primary materials. The addition of various shapes, sizes and fibers can affect the properties of the epoxy matrix composite. Therefore, the use of walnut nuts and hazelnuts is very important. As we know, the precious walnut and hazelnut use only the inside, and the shell is discarded. These shells were collected, purified, dried, sieved in a $0.06 \mu\text{m}$ sieve. The addition of filler particles of $0.06 \mu\text{m}$ to the epoxy oligomer was economically and environmentally efficient.

Formulation of the problem. As is known, epoxy oligomers possess high adhesion, but have not high thermal stability. One of its drawbacks is that the hardening process even with hardeners is very long. Adding a different natural filler to EDO seriously eliminated these problems.

The structure, physico-mechanical and operational properties of a composition based on an epoxy oligomer have been studied. To study these properties, various modern methods of investigation have been used. IR spectra were collected for each component and analyzed. The force of tightening and bending of the obtained composite material has been studied.

For all components of the composite, IR spectra were taken (Figure 5 (a) (b) (c)). The compositions were examined by infrared spectroscopy on a NICOLET Is10 spectrometer.

Fig. 5. IR spectra of components: walnut (a), hazelnut (b), ED-20 (d) and filled with ED-20 (c)

In the IR spectrum of the absorption band, $\nu_{\text{OH}} = 3478 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ refers to the vibrational O-H bond vibrations in the dimer state. On the spectrum, one can also observe absorption bands at $\nu_{\text{CH}} = 3073 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ pertaining to alkenes or an aromatic nucleus. The series of bands that are from $\nu = 2599-1961 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ refer to the characteristic bands of hazelnut absorption. All other absorption bands belong to DMF.

The same can be said about the filler - walnut.

After the interaction of the fillers and the hardener with the resin on the IR spectra, it can be seen that the O-H group in the resin molecule with the absorption band centered at $\nu_{\text{OH}} = 3296.68 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ for walnut, $\nu_{\text{OH}} = 3292.89 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ for hazelnuts, $\nu_{\text{OH}} = 3288.80 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ for wood flour. In general, the spectrum remained unchanged compared to the spectrum of pure resin without fillers and hardener.

The technological properties of the composition depend on the chemical nature and the structure of the hardeners. The process of curing resins at temperatures of 20 - 200 °C. The process is a complex multi-stage process. As a result of the interaction of the hardener with the resin, it passes into a cross-linked spatial structure. In our work, we used a hardener hardener - a representative of the amine series PEPA.

To study the curing process of the epoxy resin, samples were prepared in the following manner and the following composition. These samples were subjected to the following analyzes: the cure rate of each sample

was determined, the degree of cure, the adhesive properties, the chemical resistance to various solvents and sea water.

The degree of curing of the compositions as a function of the curing time and the additives administered was studied by extraction with acetone in a Soxhlet apparatus. Samples were ground to a powdery state. Then 1-2 g of the crushed sample was wrapped in filter paper in such a way that the powder did not pour from the paper. On the filter paper, the designations for each sample were put and placed in the apparatus

Curing of samples was carried out both at room temperature and by heating in the oven to certain temperatures.

Table 2.

Degree of curing of compositions with different fillers

The curing temperature	ED-20 /Without filler	ED-20 /Walnut	ED-20 /Hazelnut
20	78.0	93,3	92,7
60	82.1	95	95,7
90	89,5	96,8	97,3
120	91,4	97.3	98.2

The amount of hardener in the manufactured compositions varied from 10 to 15.5 parts by weight. The experiments showed that if the hardener is taken in an amount of 10-11.5 parts by weight, the composition will have low physical and mechanical strength properties. The best stable properties are observed at 10 parts by mass, and the reaction proceeds with the release of heat. Also in a small amount of hardener, even if the

sample is cured for several days, the coating is sticky. An increase in the amount of hardener or higher than 15.5 parts by weight is also not desirable, since the sample acquires excessive strength, stiffness, is obtained with deteriorated properties. Thermally cured epoxy compounds are more impact-resistant, impact resistance 3-4 times greater than those rejected at room temperature.

Table 3.

Properties of epoxy compositions

Indicators of compositions	I	II	III
Breaking stress at bending, MPa	14	15	17
Impact strength, kJ / m	2	2	3
Brinell hardness, MPa	170	250	225
Degree of cure after 24 hours	15 -20	5-7	5-7

In most cases, the fillers used for the resin are the wastes of any production. Their application for any purpose is positive. They reduce costs and improve the technological and operational properties of epoxy compositions. The properties of two different fillers have been studied: Walnut, Hazelnut.

The practical interest of the process is to create highly filled materials and, in order to use them in various industrial environments, a thermomechanical analysis was carried out, the results of which showed that the filled materials had low deformation in a highly elastic state and a high glass transition temperature.

The resulting filled material can be used as a protective coating film for metal products, as adhesive with increased elasticity and adhesion, material for bulk floors. The best properties have compositions, the ratio of the reagents in which the resin is made: a filler of 50:30% by weight.

The curing process of ED-20 resin with fillers was investigated: walnut, hazelnuts. The degree of curing of epoxy resin was determined depending on the ratio of the reagents: resin, oil, hardener and fillers. Samples without fillers acquired a degree of curing no more than 92.7%, filled samples - 99.6%.

The chemical resistance of the cured resin ED-20 in aggressive media was determined. The highest chemical resistance was found in a sample filled with hazelnut

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